

Hybrid Work Models and Work Life Balance in the IT Sector: A Review of Literature.

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ABSTRACT

Hybrid work models have emerged and become widely used as a result of the recent rapid transition of workplace structures, especially in the Information Technology (IT) industry. For businesses seeking to enhance employee autonomy while maintaining operational effectiveness, hybrid work is a blend of remote and in office work arrangements that has emerged as a key strategy. The purpose of this review paper is to analyze and summarize the body of research on hybrid work models and how they affect employee work life balance and organizational productivity in the IT sector. The paper also emphasizes how organizational policies and technology adoption can facilitate hybrid work settings. Academic databases and scholarly repositories were used to find relevant studies. The literature was examined and categorized into major thematic areas, such as the evolution of work models, the role of hybrid work in the IT industry, the effects of hybrid work on work life balance and employee wellbeing, the impact of organizational policies and technology adoption techniques in managing hybrid teams. According to the research findings, hybrid work models offer a number of advantages, such as increased flexibility, higher employee happiness, shorter commutes, and possible productivity increases. The literature does, however, also draw attention to a number of difficulties, including poor communication, trouble coordinating teams, problems managing work life boundaries, and the requirement for strong organizational support and leadership. The assessment also identifies significant research gaps, including the lack of long term analysis and the inadequate investigation of mediating factors such as organizational policy and technological uptake. In order to better understand the long-term effects of hybrid work models on people and companies in the IT sector, the study further recommends future research directions.

Keywords: IT Sector, Technology Adoption, Work Life Balance, Organizational Policies, Hybrid Work Model, Wellbeing,

INTRODUCTION:

1.1 Concept of Hybrid Work Model

The term "hybrid" generally refers to a blend or combination of something. In other words, a hybrid workplace paradigm is a flexible work environment. It combines office and remote work. Especially after the pandemic, "hybrid work" suggests businesses are adopting both offline and online work modes. They do this to improve growth and productivity for themselves and their employees (B. Vidhyaa, 2022).

1.2 Forms of Hybrid Work Model (B. Vidhyaa, 2022).

Flexible hybrid work arrangement: Depending on their objectives, employees can select their locations and working hours under this arrangement

Fixed hybrid work: In this scenario, companies set the days and times that workers must be in the office and work remotely.

Office-First hybrid work: Employees have been on-site for the job in addition to having the opportunity to work remotely a few days a week.

Remote-First hybrid work: Workers can visit workstations or places for training, team development, and cooperation, but they mostly operate offline.

1.3 Benefits of Hybrid Work Model

According to authors, the COVID-19 pandemic hastened the transition from traditional office work to remote work, prompting businesses to embrace hybrid work models as a long-term fix. The paper emphasize that opportunities for in-person cooperation are combined with the advantages of distant flexibility in hybrid work. The study highlights that in order to effectively manage hybrid teams and sustain productivity and employee engagement, firms must rethink work processes, digital infrastructure, and workplace culture (Hilberath, et al., 2020).

Some of the benefits are as follows (Bloom, et al., 2024):

Cost reduction
Increased productivity
Fewer commutes
Better work life balance
Higher employee satisfaction

1.4 Challenges of Hybrid Work Model:

Overcoming certain obstacles is crucial for the new normal model to be implemented successfully. According to the "Harvard Business Review," implementing the new normal model presents a number of typical difficulties (Haas, 2022) .

Communication (technical issues were encountered)
Coordination (both employers and employees must put forth greater effort to collaborate in a hybrid form)
Relationship (both personal and professional)
Innovations

Culture (new hires must be integrated into the company's norms and socialized).

1.5 Work Life Balance

The definition of work-life balance is "equal time or priority to personal and professional activities." This involves striking a balance between personal, professional, and family needs. In cultures where money is primarily created and dispersed through labor markets, it can be characterized as "the relationship between the institutional and cultural times and spaces of work and non-work" (Felstead, et al., 2022).

1.6 Importance of Work life balance in Hybrid work model

Employers have implemented a new regular work style known as "hybrid work arrangements" in response to the observation that employees are unwilling to return to their offices in full mode following COVID-19. According to HP's Global Study (Inc., 2022), hybridity is highly preferred by Indian employees due to its higher productivity and increased flexibility to enhance work-life balance. The study also suggests that in the future, there should be a greater focus on the components of work that include collaboration and equity. Maintaining appropriate timetables for both official and personal work is crucial to achieving a healthy work-life balance in daily living.

1.7 Role of IT Company's

IT companies play a pivot role in implementing a new normal model, given their changing work patterns, technology-driven processes and high tech employees. As their operations mainly rely on cloud-based systems, collaboration tools, and virtual communication platforms, these companies were among the first to implement remote and hybrid work arrangements. IT firms improve work-life balance by offering employees flexibility through the implementation of hybrid work practices, which enable them to handle both personal and professional obligations.

2. Scope of the paper

The review examines literature on hybrid work arrangements and their impact on work-life balance in the IT industry. It addresses key themes such as technology adoption, organizational policies, employee wellbeing, work life balance, and shifts in work dynamics in hybrid settings. Publications from 2017 to 2025 are reviewed to highlight the evolution of hybrid practices, especially during transitions to flexible setups.

The review examines journal articles and scholarly publications relevant to the topic. The analysis primarily emphasizes studies conducted in India, supplemented by select global comparisons, to provide insight into the effects of hybrid work within organizational and technological contexts. By synthesizing these studies, the review seeks to summarize current knowledge and identify areas requiring further research.

2.1 Objectives of the Review

To analyse existing literature on hybrid work models, work life balance in IT sector.

To integrate and classify the findings of previous studies related to key themes.

To assess and identify the future research gaps in the current literature and highlight areas for future research on hybrid work and work-life balance.

2.2 Research Methodology

The current research undergoes previous studies blended work modes and work life balance in the IT company's using a thematic literature review methodology. Research papers and scholarly journal articles about digital adoption, work life balance, hybrid work, and organizational policies that were published between 2017 and 2025 were taken into consideration. Papers related to non-IT sectors were not included. The chosen papers were subjected to theoretical and thematic analysis in order to identify considerable gaps in literature and suggest future course of action.

3. Review of Literature Based on Major Themes

3.1 Evolution of Hybrid work Model

Post COVID, the desire for better work-life balance has led to an increase in the popularity of blended work settings. The study used a mixed method analysis to investigate how hybrid work models impact employee performance, wellbeing, and business results. Key findings indicate that while hybrid work promotes flexibility, improved work life balance, and increased autonomy, it also leads to obstacles in communication and feelings of loneliness in employees. The majority of findings are based on short term observations, and gaps include insufficient longitudinal data and industry specific insights. In order to better understand the implications of hybrid mode, the study recommends that future research to employ larger samples, cross-industry comparisons, and long-term impact studies (Andreeva, 2022).

The purpose of the study was to evaluate how hybrid work practices affected corporate governance and employee involvement in the post COVID workplace and was based on surveys among workers in different companies. According to the report, hybrid work increases flexibility,

engagement, and satisfaction, but it also poses problems for company management, transparency, and supervision. The study points out several key limitations, such as not analyzing long-term governance effects, focusing too much on short term results, and only looking at a few sectors. To better understand how hybrid employment affects workers and organization, the authors recommend more research in different industries, with larger sample sizes and long term studies (Sethi, et al., 2022).

As per the analysis that 84.4% of workers thought the mixed work approach was successful, because employees may select between working remotely and on site, the results demonstrated a favourable hybrid work arrangement with higher employee satisfaction. Although some employees had trouble coordinating and communicating, the study revealed that hybrid work typically had a favourable impact on job performance and enhanced work life balance and employee happiness. Gaps include a lack of longitudinal data and restricted generalizability as a result of a single company focus. To better understand the results of hybrid work, the authors suggest conducting long-term studies and bigger, cross industry samples in the future (Santillan, et al., 2023).

3.2 Work life Balance

The study's objectives are to perceive the work related and demographic variables affecting work life balance and to suggest ways of improvisation. The research recognizes the difficulty in managing work and personal obligations, particularly in light of evolving family and work arrangements. To collect data, the study employs a mixed method approach that includes surveys and interviews. According to the findings, smart HR practices can raise worker happiness and productivity in the "IT sector." It demands ongoing observation and assessment of work life balance programs as well as investigation of the changing dynamics of it in IT, taking into account new developments in technology and shifting work styles (Adupa, & Boora, 2024).

The Literature review examined the organizational and family aspects of the factors influencing the work life balance of women professionals in the IT industry. The study found that the work life balance is greatly impacted by workload, long hours, family obligations, and organizational support; flexible policies can increase satisfaction. The limitations include low generalizability and an exclusive focus on women in certain IT organizations. In order to promote work life balance for female IT professionals, the report suggests doing more extensive research across industries and creating inclusive HR policies (Gupta, et al., 2021).

The primary contribution of the research is the significance of "true autonomy and flexibility" for employees in mixed work contexts. The study highlights how social networks, work life balance, and life happiness are positively correlated with hybrid work. Additionally, the study emphasizes the value of hybrid labor in unpredictable and unstable circumstances like those brought about by the COVID 19 epidemic (Mishra & Bharti, 2024).

3.3 WellBeing in Hybrid mode

The condition known as "technostress" occurs when people find it difficult to adjust to or manage new information and communication technology, which has detrimental effects on their attitudes, thoughts, behaviour, and physical health. It has been discovered that technostress poses serious hazards to organizational performance and work life balance. These elements pose risk to work life balance, productivity, job security, and general wellbeing at work, requiring people to pursue ongoing education (Bencsik & Juhasz, 2023).

Health and safety, self actualization and self respect, economic and social, knowledge, and aesthetic criteria were among the characteristics that were the focus of the study. The authors are aware of future research that may focus on potential challenges and strategies to support employees' general wellbeing and job satisfaction throughout the transition period (Sri & Vasantha, 2024).

3.4 IT Company's

Flexibility in work life balance boosts employee dedication and talent, making it crucial to IT success. IT workers were not able to balance out between work and personal life. The study discovered that while flexible schedules and supportive management practices increase employee happiness but long work hours, stress, and workload had a detrimental effect on work life balance. There are gaps such as a small sample size, an emphasis on a small number of IT firms, and no investigation on long term impact. In order to improve work life balance in the IT sector, the report suggests more investigation into organizational policies and practices (Amritha, et al., 2017).

Additionally, research investigated the organizational, people, and financial impacts of POST COVID work practices within the Indian IT sector. The study's main findings were that despite infrastructural and sociocultural challenges, IT companies have widely adopted work from home and hybrid models to maintain day to day activities, improve flexibility. However, the study's short study period, small sample size, and lack of quantitative/empirical validation were its drawbacks. Larger sample sizes, employee/top management surveys, and an evaluation of the long term operational and financial effects should all be part of future research (Kolluru, et al., 2021).

3.5 Organizational policies and practices

Employee health, productivity, work life balance and individual and team performance are all enhanced by hybrid working, which blends office and remote work and offers more flexibility and control over working modes. Over the past ten years, firms have implemented a variety of telework and flexible work arrangements. In order to retain top talent and maintain competitiveness, employees strongly encourage work from home rules and changes to the workplace culture (Ateeq, 2022).

The study focuses on how employees in "Russian IT sector companies" focus on "work practices and attitudes"

toward remote and hybrid work settings. It looks at job responsibilities and employees' sociopsychological health under new work arrangements. Additionally, the study looks at how effective flexible workplaces are for both individuals and groups, as well as the management and organizational elements that shape workers' perceptions of remote work (Balabanova & Molchanova, 2022).

The study examines the "merits and demerits" of various workplace cultures, particularly the hybrid model, among workers in several Indian industry sectors. According to the report, most employees prefer the hybrid model because it offers a work life balance. Nonetheless, the study emphasizes how important it is for employers and employees to comprehend and embrace the hybrid model more fully. Companies and employees can use the study's findings as a guide to create an action plan for successfully implementing the hybrid model (Sankar & Malhotra, 2023).

3.6 Adoption of Technology in Hybrid Work Frameworks

The study suggests redefining "antecedents of work engagement in work settings," such as excessive technology use and work family conflict. The review TABLE 4.1

suggests work life balance principles to help people balance work and family, especially while addressing technological difficulties in a remote work setting, to reduce burnout and overflow. It stresses the necessity of ICT assistance and device and application training (Kanengoni, 2023).

The study examines the development of Human Resource Management practices in the ear of new normal model within global digital transformation. Furthermore, the key findings also indicate that there is a growing body of study on work-life balance, employee engagement, digital leadership, and technology utilization in hybrid work environments. To promote sustainable HR practices in hybrid work settings, more empirical and interdisciplinary research is needed, as there is a gap in how human resource management methods successfully integrate with digital technology in actual organizational practices (Asriani & Syamsiah, 2025).

4. Summary Analysis Table of Thematic Literature Review based upon Literature Reviews

S. No.	Author & Year	Themes	Purpose	key Findings	Research Gaps	Future Approach	Methodology
1	(Amritha, et al., 2017)	Role of IT Company's	To know the effect of job demands on WLB in IT sector	Flexible schedules increased happiness, but resulted into long hours, stress and more of work load	Small sample size, less IT company's undertaken, no focus was on long term impact	To target more IT companies and investigate into clearer organizational policies for better WLB in IT.	Quantitative analysis
2	(Kolluru, et al., 2021)	Role of IT Company's	To assess organizational and personnel effects of the work practices	WFH and hybrid work are essential for operations, flexibility, and client service despite sociocultural and infrastructure challenges.	Small sample, short term analysis	Adopt empirical analysis, large sample size	Mixed method approach
3	(Gupta, et al., 2021)	Work Life Balance	Identification of factors affecting work life balance of women in IT sector	Flexibility enhances satisfaction, factors identified like workload, stress, working hours, organization support	Limited generalizability	To develop inclusive HR policies	Quantitative survey

4	(Andreeva , 2022).	Evolution Hybrid Work Model	To achieve improved employee well-being, better work-life balance, and creativity	Results showed improved work life balance, flexibility, higher autonomy	Feeling of isolation, lack of communication	long term analysis, large sample usage	mixed method approach
5	(Sethi, et al., 2022	Evolution Hybrid Work Model	To examine how hybrid work practices affect corporate governance and employee engagement in the post-COVID workplace	Employee flexibility, engagement, and satisfaction are all enhanced by hybrid work	Short term evaluation and restricted sector coverage	Longitudinal studies with large samples	Survey
6	(Santillan, et al., 2023).	Evolution Hybrid Work Model	To investigate the effect of hybrid work model on employee happiness, work-life balance, and job execution	Hybrid mode had a beneficial impact on job execution and enhanced work-life balance and employee happiness.	Limited generalizability as a result of the lack of longitudinal data and the single-company focus.	Longitudinal studies with large samples	Mixed method approach
7	(Mishra & Bharti, 2024).	Work Life Balance	This research aims to investigate the relationship between work-life balance (WLB), social support (SS), and life satisfaction (SWL) in the context of hybrid work (HW)	Hybrid job correlated positively with work life balance, social life, and social support.	Restricted sector coverage and sample	Longitudinal studies and larger, more varied populations to be used	Survey

			in learning companies				
8	(Adupa, & Boora, 2024).	Work Life Balance	Understanding the work-related and demographic factors influencing work life balance.	It impacts performance, productivity, and job satisfaction. Remote work, flexible schedules, efficient task management, and strong organizational support affect WLB.	Implementation of strategic HR policies	Future research should examine work dynamics in the IT industry while considering the effects of technological advances and changing labor habits.	Mixed method approach
9	(Bencsik & Juhasz, 2023)	Well Being in Hybrid mode	This study seeks to identify the most significant technostress risk factors that jeopardize workers' work performance and work-life balance.	The results demonstrate that high levels of technostress have a detrimental impact on mental health, job satisfaction, and work-life balance	Respondents' unwillingness to answer	Large samples, other factors to explore	Survey(questionnaire)
10	(Sri & Vasantha, 2024).	Well Being in Hybrid mode	To examine how well the hybrid workplace affects organizational commitment in the chosen IT firms	Employee productivity and well-being are improved by hybrid models, and these factors are closely associated with increased job satisfaction	Small sample size	Focus on Long-term evaluation of organizational commitment and hybrid work, work upon large samples	Quantitative analysis
11	(Ateeq, 2022)	Organizational policies & practices	To understand the hybrid work model concept, its advantages , and challenges in modern organizations	The results show that hybrid work enhances flexibility, productivity, and employee satisfaction but hinders communication, collaboration, and management.	Restricted empirical research	Long-term implications, employee performance, and organizational strategies for hybrid work deployment should be researched.	Literature Review Approach

12	(Balabano va & Molchano va, 2022).	Organizational policies & practices	To assess IT company employees' remote and hybrid work environments and their effects on work practices and employee experiences.	Hybrid and remote work increase flexibility and autonomy but lacks communication, collaboration, and work-life balance.	Sample scope and regional emphasis limitations	Future investigations into the enduring effects of mixed work and organizational methodologies for efficient staff management.	Empirical methodology based on surveys
13	(Sankar & Malhotra, 2023).	Organizational policies & practices	To analyze the synergy of hybrid work with organizational culture to ascertain its impact on employee collaboration and workplace dynamics	Hybrid work provides autonomy and adaptability but had difficulties in sustaining company culture, collaboration, and communication	Limited scope and absence of long-term empirical evidence	The study propose that future research should investigate the long-term effects of hybrid work on organizational culture and employee engagement, as well as cultural adaptation strategies.	Literature review
14	(Kanengoni, 2023).	Technology adoption	Investigated the link between technostress, perceived organizational support, work-family conflict, and job engagement in hybrid and virtual work environments.	The results demonstrate that while good organizational support enhances employee engagement and balance, high levels of technostress and work-family conflict lower job engagement.	Limited sample coverage	Proper work life balance policies, adequate information communication support, defining clear boundaries between work and personal life.	Survey
15	(Asriani & Syamsiah, 2025)	Technology adoption	To examine Human Resource	Research on digital leadership, employee engagement, work-	Absence of real-world implementation studies and a	Suggest further empirical and multidisciplinary study to create	Bibliometric

			Management (HRM) research trends in the context of global digital revolution and hybrid work.	life balance, and technology flexibility in hybrid work environments is increasing as per findings drawn	restricted integration of HR policies with new digital technology.	sustainable and successful HRM procedures for hybrid workplaces	Analyses
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5. Recommendation and Conclusion

The thematic literature summarizes the growing importance of the new normal model, especially in the IT sector due to changes in workplace patterns. The majority of studies says that hybrid work contributes positively to flexibility, job satisfaction, better work life balance and improved autonomy (Amritha, et al., 2017) and (Andreeva, 2022). Additionally, studies also throw light on the role of organizations support, HR policies and social support systems in increasing employee engagement and well-being in blended environments (Mishra & Bharti, 2024; Kanengoni, 2023; Asriani & Syamsiah, 2025). On the other hand, some research points to drawbacks such as mental stress, technostress, lack of communication, feeling of isolation, work-family conflict, and problems in maintaining organizational culture and collaboration (Bencsik & Juhasz, 2023), (Balabanova & Molchanova, 2022), (Sankar & Malhotra, 2023).

Although the review spotlights many contributions, there were some under researched areas. For example, the majority of the analysis is restricted by small sample sizes and short term analysis, few IT companies (Kolluru, et al., 2021) . Furthermore, there is less study on the long term impact of blended work on employee productivity, organizational commitment, and governance structures (Ateeq, 2022). In light of these gaps, researchers' future possible focus shall be on large scale empirical research as well as longitudinal analysis to perceive the prolonged effects of hybrid work models (Sri & Vasantha, 2024). Continued research on human resource strategies, leadership practices, and technology management is therefore necessary to support the development of sustainable and effective hybrid work systems.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement: Since the study employed secondary sources to get fresh insights, all data were appropriately cited in the report.

Ethical Responsibility: The study does not include any human subjects or animals. Consequently, ethical approval was not needed.

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